

PBL in the Teaching of Differential Equations from Bachelor to Engineer

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Abstract

This paper will present the use of the PBL active learning method in the teaching of Differential equations from bachelor of engineering study programmes at the Faculty of Mechanical Engineering at the Slovak University of Technology in Bratislava.

PBL is an educational approach that focuses on using real-world problems to support student learning. Therefore, we want to emphasize its importance in teaching Mathematics – why we need it, in which mathematical courses we can use it, how to incorporate PBL into mathematics courses, where we can find it, what can students use to solve PBL, and how we want to proceed with PBL further.

The paper is concluded with a demonstration of one PBL used in two mathematics courses – in the basic course Mathematics II at the bachelor's degree of study and in the Applied Mathematics course at the master's degree of study.

Introduction

Mathematics represents one of the fundamental pillars for mastering specialized courses at technical universities. Secondary school graduates often struggle to meet the demands of university-level mathematics and to work independently, systematically, and apply their already acquired mathematical knowledge. Active learning methods such as Problem-Based Learning (PBL) and eduScrum help students overcome these challenges. PBL shows students where and how mathematics is continuously used in specialized technical courses. EduScrum develops students' soft skills, such as the ability to work in a team, share responsibility for solving tasks, and more. Based on our previous experiences, students' feedback on these methods has been very positive and their opinion was collected through an evaluation questionnaire (Gabková, Letavaj, Velichová (2022)).

Differential equations form the theoretical foundation of most engineering courses at the bachelor's and master's levels of study at the Faculty of Mechanical Engineering at the Slovak University of Technology (FME STU). They are taught in the basic course Mathematics II in the curriculum Ordinary Differential equations at the bachelor's degree of study and in the Applied Mathematics course at the master's degree of study. The Applied Mathematics course has been taught since 2018 and was designed specifically for masters degree students of the study programme Automobiles and Mobile Working Machines.

It is necessary to introduce PBL into teaching mathematics in the first year of study at the university because

1. they demonstrate where and how Mathematics can be used continually in special technical courses,

2. students learn to work with the nomenclature, that is used in technical courses (see Table 1.),
3. students become aware of the parallel between the conceptual apparatus of Mathematics and technical courses (see Table 2.),
4. they give students the opportunity to develop and test acquired knowledge and skills in Mathematics directly through problems they might face in the real-world situations,
5. students better understand the importance of numerical methods in engineering education.

Table 1. The nomenclature in the Maths and Technical courses

	Mathematics course	Technical courses
Different variables	$y = y(x)$	$u = u(t)$
Constants denoted generally	$g = 9.81 \text{ ms}^{-2}$	g (only in general)
Different notation of differential equation	$y'' = y''(t)$	$\frac{d^2u}{dt^2} = u''(t) = \ddot{u}(t)$

Table 2. The conceptual apparatus in the Maths and Technical courses

Mathematics course	Technical courses
The stationary point of a function	The equilibrium position of a system
Eigenvalues of the matrix	The stability of a system with forced oscillations
Transformation of the motion equation into a system of the 1 st order linear differential equations	Transformation of the motion equation into a state space

Practical experiences in teaching mathematics show how it is important to select problems for PBL from the lecture notes for specialised subjects taught at the faculty. Why? The advantage of these applications is that once in further study students "will remember them!". Special technical text books (Starek (2009), Žičar (2003)) exist for study programme Applied Mechanics and Mechanics at the FME STU that are a rich source of PBLs for a teacher of Mathematics. However, the inclusion of these PBLs in mathematics teaching also requires close cooperation between the mathematics teacher and the teacher of technical courses in this study programme.

Some PBL equations can be hand-solved, but most of them require a solution using numerical methods and with the support of some software. FME STU students use Mathematica software, a table of formulas of numerical methods and Wolfram Mathematica type files containing short programmes to solve more demanding PBL equations using numerical methods. Each student "composes" his solution of the project using these short programmes with numerical methods, graphs of numerical methods and evaluation of errors in numerical solution. Why Wolfram Mathematica? Because it is a

simple tool that allows to simulate and to solve calculation-intensive tasks of real-world situations through its symbolic and visualization options.

Demonstration of PBL in courses at the bachelor's and master's degree of study

Short introduction to a PBL topic. Car passengers are exposed to fatigue and unwanted vibrations that affect their health. Undesirable vibrations (in the vertical, longitudinal and transverse direction) occur when the car drives on an uneven road. For the vertical direction of oscillation, it is necessary to avoid the frequency band in the range of 4-8 Hz (the natural frequency of the human organism in the abdomen), which causes nausea. Several models of the car - quarter, half and full are used to simulate the oscillation of the car, its non-spring-loaded and spring-loaded masses when driving on an uneven road at different speeds. The behaviour of the car when driving on an uneven road allows us to know the solution of the equations of motion for the corresponding model of the car in the physical and state space.

The following PBL was selected from the special technical text book by Starek (2009).

Príklad 3.2 ✓
 Bežným príkladom kmitania s kinematickým budením je pohyb automobilu po nerovnej ceste, resp. pohyb lietadla po rozbehovej dráhe. V tomto príklade treba vyšetriť vplyv rýchlosti a hmotnosti športového automobilu na amplitúdu kmitania. Ekvivalentné hodnoty tuhosti a tlmenia odpruženia automobilu sú $4 \cdot 10^5 \text{ N/m}$, $2 \cdot 10^4 \text{ Ns/m}$ hmotnosť je 1007 kg. Matematický model cesty je daný vzťahom $y(t) = 0,01 \sin \omega_b t$. Frekvencia budenia od cesty je $f_b = v/\lambda$, kde v je rýchlosť automobilu v km/h a λ je vlnová dĺžka nerovnosti v km. Platí, že $f = \omega/2\pi$, a po dosadení máme

$$\omega_b = 2\pi v/\lambda = 2\pi v/(3600 \cdot 0,006) = 0,291 \text{ rad/s}$$

Figure 1. The special technical text book and the selected PBL

- **PBL in the basic Mathematics II course at the bachelor degree of study**

A sports car weighing $m = 1000 \text{ kg}$ moves along an uneven road in time T at a constant speed. The mathematical model of the uneven road is given by function $u(t) = \sin(t)$. Example values of the stiffness and damping of the automobile suspension are $k = 2000 \text{ Nm}^{-1}$ and $b = 2000 \text{ Nsm}^{-1}$.

Movement of the car on the uneven road represents a real system with forced oscillation. The behaviour of the car (oscillating system) when driving on an uneven road allows us to know the solution of the equation of motion for a quarter model of a car with 1 degree of freedom in the physical space

$$\begin{aligned}
 m\ddot{x} + b(\dot{x} - \dot{u}) + k(x - u) &= 0 \\
 x(0) &= 0 \\
 \dot{x}(0) &= 0
 \end{aligned}$$

where

$x = x(t)$ – a deflection of a car moving on an uneven road

Figure 2. Quarter model with 1 degree of freedom of a car moving on uneven road

Task 1. Adjust the motion equation to the basic form.

$$\text{Solution: } m\ddot{x} + b(\dot{x} - \dot{u}) + k(x - u) = 0 \rightarrow \ddot{x} + 2\dot{x} + 2x = 2 \sin t + 2 \cos t$$

Task 2. Find the deflection of a car moving on an uneven road in time T .

Solution: The particular solution $x_p(t)$ of non-homogeneous ODE II is

$$x_p(t) = -\frac{4}{5} e^{-t} \sin(t) + \frac{2}{5} e^{-t} \cos(t) - \frac{2}{5} \cos(t) + \frac{6}{5} \sin(t); t \in [0, T]; T > 0$$

Task 3. Interpret the results about a car moving on an uneven road in physical units

$$x(3) = 0,54; \dot{x}(3) = -1,07; \ddot{x}(3) = -0,64$$

- **PBL in the course Applied Mathematics at the master's degree of study**

A car is moving along an uneven road in time T at a constant speed. The mathematical model of the uneven road is given by function $u(t)$. Movement of the non-spring-loaded masses and spring-loaded masses of the car on the uneven road represents a real system with forced oscillation.

The behaviour of the car (oscillating system) when driving on an uneven road allows us to know the solution of the motion equations for a quarter model of a car with 2 degrees of freedom in the physical space

$$\begin{aligned}
 m_1 \ddot{x}_1 + k_1(x_1 - u) - k_2(x_2 - x_1) - b_2(\dot{x}_2 - \dot{x}_1) &= 0 & x_1(0) = 0, \dot{x}_1(0) = 0 \\
 m_2 \ddot{x}_2 + k_2(x_2 - x_1) + b_2(\dot{x}_2 - \dot{x}_1) &= 0 & x_2(0) = 0, \dot{x}_2(0) = 0
 \end{aligned}$$

Figure 3. Quarter model with 2 degrees of freedom of a car moving on uneven road

where

– the mathematical model of an uneven road $u(t) = A \sin(t)$; $A = 0.05$ m – the amplitude

– non spring-loaded masses of a car $x_1 = x_1(t)$ – a deflection

$m_1 = 386.48$ kg – a mass

$k_1 = 1.2528 \cdot 10^6$ Nm⁻¹ – a radial stiffness

coefficient of the tyre

– spring-loaded masses of a car

$x_2 = x_2(t)$ – a deflection

$m_2 = 2628.7$ kg – a mass

$k_2 = 2.0597 \cdot 10^5$ Nm⁻¹ – a coefficient

of the spring stiffness

$b_2 = 6.722 \cdot 10^3$ Nsm⁻¹ – a damping

coefficient of oil shock absorber

Task 1. Transform motion equations (ME) into the state space and solve further tasks in this space. Write motion equations in matrix form for both space.

Solution:

ME in the physical space: $M \cdot \ddot{\bar{x}}(t) + B \cdot \dot{\bar{x}}(t) + K \cdot \bar{x}(t) = \bar{F}(t)$; $\bar{x}(0) = \bar{0}$; $\bar{x}'(0) = \bar{0}$

ME in the state space: $\bar{z}'(t) = A \cdot \bar{z}(t) + \bar{f}(t)$; $\bar{z}'(0) = \bar{0}$

$$\begin{pmatrix} z_1'(t) \\ z_2'(t) \\ z_3'(t) \\ z_4'(t) \end{pmatrix} = \begin{pmatrix} 0 & 1 & 0 & 0 \\ \frac{-k_1 - k_2}{m_1} & \frac{-b_2}{m_1} & \frac{k_2}{m_1} & \frac{b_2}{m_1} \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 1 \\ \frac{k_2}{m_2} & \frac{b_2}{m_2} & \frac{-k_2}{m_2} & \frac{-b_2}{m_2} \end{pmatrix} \cdot \begin{pmatrix} z_1(t) \\ z_2(t) \\ z_3(t) \\ z_4(t) \end{pmatrix} + \begin{pmatrix} 0 \\ \frac{k_1}{m_1} u(t) \\ 0 \\ 0 \end{pmatrix}; \begin{pmatrix} z_1(0) \\ z_2(0) \\ z_3(0) \\ z_4(0) \end{pmatrix} = \begin{pmatrix} 0 \\ 0 \\ 0 \\ 0 \end{pmatrix}$$

Task 2. Based on presented graphs of numerical solutions, can one state, that the acceleration of the non-sprung-loaded and sprung-loaded masses of the car are dampened after a certain time?

i.e. The car's movement on the uneven road will be stabilized?

Solution:

Figure 4. Dampening of accelerations of both masses of a car

Task 3. Display a deflection and a velocity of the non-spring-loaded and spring-loaded masses of a car at time $t \in [0,10]$ in sec using Euler's method with step $h = 0,01$. If the method is not stable for the given step h, modify step h so that it is stabilized.

Solution:

The unstable Euler's method ($h = 0,01$) The stable Euler's method ($h = 0,001$)
the deflection of a car

Figure 5. Non-spring-loaded masses of a car

The unstable Euler's method ($h = 0,01$) The stable Euler's method ($h = 0,001$)
the deflection of a car

Figure 6. Spring-loaded masses of a car

Comment. Task 2. and Task 3. were solved using numerical methods and the software Wolfram Mathematica.

Conclusions for Education

The teaching process is based on cooperation between the teacher and the students. Therefore, in this process, not only the teacher but also the students must be active. (Maňák, Švec 2003). PBL is a teaching method by which students learn to use mathematics by actively engaging in real and meaningful projects. The PBL method, combined with the eduScrum approach, is what drives students' motivation and learning.

Therefore, we have decided to continue using PBL in the future. We have already selected additional topics involving suitable application problems to show first-year bachelor's students how and where mathematics is used in specialized technical subjects. At the same time, we aim to better prepare master's students in the *Automobiles and Mobile Working Machines* study program for their diploma theses.

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